

FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT IN RURAL AREA

Dr. Amol Gawande

Director, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India

Dr. Atul Kumar

Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India

Dr. Sheetal Darekar

Associate Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India

INTRODUCTION

Rural financial management means how to manage finance in rural areas. As we all know that rural areas are mainly dependent on agriculture and especially in India agriculture is the main source of income. All the banks provide loans to the farmer so that they can grow good quality crops which will not only fulfill the need of India but also outside India they can export good quality products and can earn good profit. Some other businesses are also much known like dairy farming, small-scale industries, handicrafts.

TYPES OF RURAL AREA BUSINESSES

Agriculture

Agriculture is the primary source of income for farmers of any country. By this the whole country can get enough food to survive, without agriculture no economy can stand for much time it is the backbone of any country. Farmers put their valuable money to sow the crop come times they take loans from the bank to buy the seeds and grow the different kinds of cereals. Sometimes they borrow money from moneylenders and some financial organizations to fulfill their needs before the harvesting of their crop they sell it into the markets and after earning money from it they repay the loan. So, the process of taking a loan from a different organization is known as rural credits.

Rural credits provider bank

nd development bank

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These are the special types of banks that provide funds to the farmer to promote the development of land and agriculture thus it increases agricultural production it mainly provides long term loan means Farmer can repayment it within 15 to 20 years which is more than sufficient time to get back the money to the bank.

2) Regional rural banks

These are the banks situated in rural areas operating in regional areas in different states of India. They provide banking facilities to rural and semi-urban areas. It includes para banking facilities like locker facilities, mobile banking, internet banking, and debit and credit card facilities to their customers.

3) Commercial banks

Commercial banks provide consumers and small to medium-size businesses with very basic banking services like deposit accounts and loans. These banks earn money from various kinds of fees and by interest income from loans. Banks usually works in physical locations, but the nowadays online facility is also provided by the banks. Commercial banks are very essential to the economy because they provide capital, credit, and liquidity in the market.

4) Government

This loan is provided by the government and is also known as the Taccavi loan it is a short-term loan provides to the farmers to buy fertilizers, seeds, equipment, and some other tools. By doing this they try to enhance the productivity of crop cultivation and help poor farmers to increase their income so they can survive in a tough situation.

5) Co-operative credit societies

This is one of the most economic sources of funding for farmers. It mainly helps medium to small-level farmers. The purpose of all the sourced of credit is to help farmers in the best possible manner to fulfill their demand regarding start their agricultural process like buy the crops and start the business and once everything is done when the crops grew well and its time to harvest it they repay the amount to the bank.

Fig. 1: Source of Credit

Dairy farm

To start a dairy farm business, one should have a few cows and buffalos at the initial level and once the business is established nicely, they can increase the number of cattle on the farm. If the owner of a dairy farm is not having enough money, they can also take a loan from the bank as we have discussed above that there are so many types of banks that promote rural businesses.

This business demands many things which need a big amount of finance like some machinery and equipment, pasteurization and storage of milk. Sheds to protect the cattle from all types of weather. They also need feed and manure storage.

CRITERIA TO GET A LOAN FOR THE DAIRY FARM

Farmers who are already in this business previously can get loans easily. An individual entrepreneur who has experience in this field can also apply for a loan. Self-help groups, NGOs, milk union cooperative society and milk federation these are the organization that can apply for the loan because there are many criteria to apply for the bank loan. There are many ways to repay the loan one can use EMI (Equated Monthly Installment) method this is the easiest method

the whole amount is divided into equal parts and a small amount can repay in every it so it's a very convenient method.

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CONCLUSION

Financial management has become so easy due to various sources that nowadays anyone can start their own business and can become financially independent as we have discussed above that many kinds of banks are available that provide loans according to the need of the customer. Agriculture and dairy farm are the most common businesses in the rural area and many people take interest to start that business because it doesn't need a high level of education and thus if a person is having basic knowledge of this business they can also start their business and banks provide every kind of loan which ranges from short term to long term so the customer can choose it according to the need and can grow their businesses and can become independent financially and support not only their families but also the nation.

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